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Abstract:

This document contains a discussion of the potential to employ a Fixed Field Accelerator (FFA) for the acceleration of muons in the MuCol study, acting as an alternative to one or more of the Rapid-Cycling Synchrotron (RCS) rings. After proposing a lattice design based on analytic formalism, this document proposes some mitigation solutions to reduce peak field in the magnets.

MuCol Consortium, 2025

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Executive summary

This document focusses on the vertical-excursion fixed field accelerator (vFFA) alternatives to the baseline design using pulsed synchrotrons. After introducing the concept and detailing the analytic model, the document proposes a set of parameters to get a stable optics for the whole energy range of the high-energy acceleration complex.

However, the constraint to minimise the orbit excursion limits the accessible parameter space. That is why this document proposes also some directions to mitigate this issue by developing decoupled, dispersion-suppressed straights insertions.

1 Introduction

This document contains a discussion of the potential to employ a Fixed Field Accelerator (FFA) for the acceleration of muons in the MuCol study, acting as an alternative to one or more of the Rapid-Cycling Synchrotron (RCS) rings. FFAs use time-independent magnetic fields (in contrast to the time-varying magnetic fields used in synchrotrons) to control machine tune and the closed orbit radius across the acceleration cycle. The discussion here focusses primarily on the concept of the Vertical-excursion Fixed Field Accelerator (vFFA), a proposed machine type wherein the closed orbit is geometrically identical for all energies, but translated vertically as a function of the energy (illustrated in Fig. 1.1), and the tune remains constant over the acceleration cycle. This condition is achieved with having fields that scale according to

$$B(z) = B_0 e^{mz}, \quad (1.1)$$

for a field B_0 at $z = 0$, where z denotes the vertical coordinate and m is a normalised field gradient (units of 1/m) chosen as a design parameter of the machine.

The use of fixed fields, rather than ramping fields, has the potential to offer a number of advantages in the context of muon acceleration. Firstly, the magnet ramp rate is no longer a constraint on the rate of acceleration, meaning that the only limitation on the rate of acceleration becomes the available integrated RF gradient. Moreover, time-independent magnetic fields eliminate the eddy current losses associated with varying magnetic fields, leading to a more energy-efficient machine - particularly when considering that these fixed magnet strengths are ideal applications of superconducting technology (by contrast, both the conventional and hybrid RCS designs proposed elsewhere in MuCol [1] require normal-conducting dipole components). On top of this, the development of power converters capable of meeting the requirements of the ramped magnets in the RCS designs represents a significant engineering challenge that would be entirely circumvented in a fixed field accelerator.

A particular advantage of the vFFA over both synchrotrons and other FFA types is that the path length is independent of the energy; as a consequence, the momentum compaction factor α_c is zero. This means that the

Fig. 1.1: An example depiction of a compact low-energy vFFA ring showing the vertical translation of the orbits as a function of energy. Note that the closed orbits exhibit curvature not only in the horizontal plane but also in the vertical plane. Shaded volumes show the magnet geometry, with the darker grey shade representing the reverse bend magnets

slip factor determining the transit time difference, given by

$$\eta = \alpha_c - \frac{1}{\gamma^2} = \frac{\frac{\Delta\tau}{\tau}}{\frac{\Delta P}{P}}, \quad (1.2)$$

in which τ is the transit time for a given momentum P , tends towards zero for highly-relativistic particles with a large Lorentz factor γ . As such, a vFFA can be considered quasi-isochronous for particles with sufficiently high momentum. In the context of the rapid acceleration required to minimise muon decay, this offers the advantage of being able to make use of on-crest acceleration, which grants a potential factor $\sqrt{2}$ gain over the synchronous phase of 135° currently selected in the RCS - thereby potentially reducing the requirements for the RF cavities. Furthermore, the time-dependent tuning of high-gradient RF cavities is another challenge that must be solved in designs with a significant change in revolution frequency over the acceleration cycle – the vFFA's isochronism offers a potential to mitigate this.

However, a number of limitations are inherent to the vFFA. The sign of the quadrupole component of the field is fixed by the sign of the dipole field, meaning that for stability in two planes, reverse-bend magnets will be required. As a consequence, the spatial efficiency of the ring is limited below the theoretical maximum computed purely from the magnetic rigidity and peak dipole field strengths. As the fields are time-independent and higher-energy orbits are stacked above lower-energy orbits, the beam centroid moves vertically between injection and extraction, meaning that large-aperture cavities will be required. Moreover, engineering fields that satisfy the scaling law will require a specialised magnet design [2] to achieve the high required dipole fields and the required field profile along the vertical gap of the magnet.

A complication associated with vFFA optics is that the 2nd-order components of the field have a skew-quadrupole effect at the region associated with peak vertical dipole field strength (with zero normal quadrupole component at this point). However, away from this region of the magnets the normal quadrupole component is non-zero. The consequence of these facts is that all curved vFFA lattices have intrinsic coupling between horizontal and vertical transverse planes, leading to difficulties in modelling the machine optics and optimising vFFA lattices, as well as issues in the design of key accelerator subsystems (such as injection and extraction devices).

This document uses the analytic formalism developed in [3] to demonstrate that stable optics can be achieved for vFFA rings based on FODO cells with footprints, energy ranges, and peak dipole fields on-orbit comparable to the RCS1 and RCS4 designs discussed in [1].

2 Analytic Design

2.1 Model details

The FODO cell of a vFFA arc is defined as a structure comprised of two vFFA magnets of opposite polarity, evenly distributed azimuthally across the cell. The magnet that bends the orbit primarily in the normal direction of the arc is referred to as the normal bend, or F-magnet, whilst the magnet with the opposite sign is referred to as the reverse bend, or D-magnet. It is assumed that the dimensions of these two magnets are independent of each other, as is the strength of their dipole fields; however, the normalised field gradient m must be equal in both magnets. The midplanes of each magnet, defined as the vertical plane in which the vertical dipole field is at its maximum and the horizontal components of the field are zero, are located at a distance r_F and r_D respectively from the arc's centre.

The geometry of the orbit through a vFFA FODO half-cell may then be parametrised as in Figure 2.1 and Table 2.1, under the assumption that the dipole fields can be considered constant along the orbit within the magnets, and zero elsewhere. As such, the closed orbit is determined by the following input parameters: the number of cells in the ring (N_c), the opening angle of the F and D magnets from the machine centre (respectively β_F and β_D – defined in terms of the intersection of the closed orbit with the magnet end planes), the radius of the orbit at the centre of the F-magnet (r_0), and the bending angle in the F-magnet (θ_F), as well as the inclination for the F-magnet, γ_F , which defines the angle of the plane of curvature within the magnet with

respect to the horizontal plane. The remaining variables that characterise the closed orbit - the bending and inclination angles of the D-magnet θ_D and γ_D , the radii of curvature ρ_F and ρ_D for each respective magnet, and the radii of the orbit with respect to machine centre at the edge of the F magnet (r_1), edge of the D-magnet (r_2), and centre of the D-magnet (r_3), alongside the distance of the drift along the closed orbit, L_s - are then computed from geometric constraints as described in Equations 2.2 to 2.7.

Table 2.1: Definitions of all input parameters and output variables that completely specify the geometry of a vFFA FODO closed orbit in terms of Fig. 2.1.

Parameter	Definition	Variable	Definition
		θ_D	$\angle CDE$
β_F	$\angle SO_3P$	ρ_F	$\overline{HJ} = \overline{JK}$
β_D	$\angle DO_2F$	ρ_D	$\overline{CD} = \overline{ED}$
$\frac{\pi}{N}$	$\angle AO_0B$	r_1	$\overline{O_4H}$
r_0	$\overline{O_5K}$	r_2	$\overline{O_1E}$
θ_F	$\angle HJK$	r_3	$\overline{O_0C}$
γ_F	$\angle SJK$	L_s	\overline{EH}
		γ_D	$\angle CDM$

The closed orbit in the vFFA must satisfy the following:

$$\theta_D = \arctan \left(\frac{\sqrt{(\tan \frac{\pi}{N} - \cos \gamma_F \tan \theta_F)^2 + \sin^2 \gamma_F \sin^2 \theta_F (\tan \frac{\pi}{N} \cos \gamma_F \tan \theta_F + 1)^2}}{\sqrt{1 - \sin^2 \gamma_F \sin^2 \theta_F (\tan \frac{\pi}{N} \cos \gamma_F \tan \theta_F + 1)}} \right), \quad (2.1)$$

$$\sin \gamma_D = \frac{\sin \theta_F}{\sin \theta_D} \sin \gamma_F, \quad (2.2)$$

$$\rho_F = r_0 \frac{\tan \beta_F}{\sin \theta_F + (1 - \cos \theta_F) \cos \gamma_F \tan \beta_F}, \quad (2.3)$$

$$r_1 = \rho_F \frac{\sin \theta_F}{\sin \beta_F}, \quad (2.4)$$

$$r_2 = r_1 \frac{\cos \beta_F + \tan \theta_F \cos \gamma_F \sin \beta_F}{\cos (\frac{\pi}{N} - \beta_D) + \tan \theta_F \cos \gamma_F \sin (\frac{\pi}{N} - \beta_D)}, \quad (2.5)$$

$$\rho_D = r_2 \frac{\sin \beta_D}{\sin \theta_D}, \quad (2.6)$$

$$r_3 = r_2 \cos \beta_D - \rho_D (1 - \cos \theta_D \cos \gamma_D). \quad (2.7)$$

Of key importance is the existence of separate inclination angles $\gamma_{F,D}$ for each magnet. It can be shown that the inclination is given by

$$\gamma_{F,D} \simeq mx_{F,D}, \quad (2.8)$$

for a normalised field gradient m and a horizontal displacement $x_{F,D}$ from the midplane of the corresponding magnet. As such, the radial positions $r_{F,D}$ of the magnet midplanes in the FODO cell must be set based on the

Fig. 2.1: 3D geometry of a closed orbit through a half-cell of a vFFA FODO lattice, beginning at the midpoint of the F-magnet and finishing at the midpoint of the D-magnet. The O_i points all lie on the central axis of the machine, and the geometry is symmetric about the radial planes passing through the centre of the F and D magnets.

radii of the closed orbit $r_{0,1,2,3}$ and the relevant inclination angles.

Once a closed orbit has been determined for the cell, it is then necessary to understand the dynamics of particles travelling around this reference orbit. To this end, a Hamiltonian for the magnet body of a vFFA magnet may be derived from the scaling law (Eq. 1.1) to give

$$\mathcal{H} \simeq \frac{\tilde{p}_x^2}{2} + \frac{\tilde{p}_z^2}{2} - \frac{1}{\rho + \frac{\sin \gamma}{m}} \left[\cos \gamma \left(m + \frac{2 \sin \gamma}{\rho} \right) xz - \frac{1}{2} m (x^2 - z^2) \sin \gamma \right] - \frac{1}{\rho \left(\rho + \frac{\sin \gamma}{m} \right)} (x^2 \cos^2 \gamma + z^2 \sin^2 \gamma), \quad (2.9)$$

in which ρ is the radius of curvature associated with the main dipole field of the magnet, and x and z are the horizontal and vertical coordinates with respect to the reference particle. This reveals the focussing behaviour of the vFFA: there is a skew-quadrupole-like focussing term proportional in strength to $\cos \gamma$, and a normal-quadrupole focussing term proportional to $\sin \gamma$, as well as weak focussing terms (proportional to $1/\rho^2$). From

this Hamiltonian, a vFFA magnet transfer matrix can be derived [3].

Setting the coefficients in this transfer matrix (e.g. ρ , γ) according to the values computed using the closed orbit equations (2.1-2.8) and combining with appropriate drift matrices corresponding to the drift lengths enables the construction of a periodic transfer matrix for the cell. From the cell transfer matrix, the decoupled tunes of the system can be evaluated by computing the argument of the eigenvalues of the 4D transfer matrix.

The use of the analytic model in this way facilitates the rapid testing of stability and tunes for any given vFFA FODO configuration, provided the approximations used in derivation of the model hold (namely: the m -value should be high compared to the value of $\sin \theta_F$; the radius of curvature within the magnets is large compared to the length of the magnets; and the fringe field length is much smaller than the length of the magnet).

2.2 Lattice parameters

To show the feasibility of vFFA options for muon acceleration as alternatives to the RCS candidates outlined in [4], the goal was set of designing - using the vFFA analytic formalism - lattices that match the energy ranges and footprints of the RCS options.

First, the parameters of RCS1 were targeted, as this ring is fully normal-conducting and requires the highest magnet ramp rate. Significant energy efficiency gains could be achieved by switching to a fully superconducting design, which would be possible in a fixed-field machine such as a vFFA. For the vFFA proposal, the principal design objectives were to match the same footprint as the RCS design (a 5990 m circumference ring) whilst maintaining a peak SC dipole field on-orbit below that achievable with current technology (the LHC main dipoles operate at 8.3 T [5], so this was considered as the maximum allowable field). Simultaneously, the vertical excursion between injection and extraction must be minimised to reduce requirements on the apertures of radiofrequency cavities and magnet elements. A final consideration is the drift lengths between magnets, which must be maintained at a reasonable size (here assumed to be 1 metre at minimum) to accommodate magnet components (e.g. coil windings and cryomodule components) and diagnostic equipment.

The parameters of the stage 1 vFFA (VFFA1) and stage 4 (VFFA4) are listed in Table 2.2 and compared directly to RCS1 and RCS4 in Table 2.3. This demonstrates that a vFFA with stable optics can be achieved for the same energy ranges as RCS1 whilst exceeding all of the previously outlined constraints. In particular, the peak dipole field is at 6.93 T, and the excursion is smaller than 5 cm.

Likewise, the development of a vFFA alternative to RCS4 was also identified as a potential avenue in which gains could be made - principally due to the fact that RCS4 has the highest path length difference over its acceleration cycle, which has the potential to increase requirements for tuning the RF.

2.3 Optics repository

The Jupyter notebook containing the analytic model of the lattice for stages 1 and 4 of the vFFA described in this document is available in Ref. [7] within the folder `high_energy_complex/vFFAx/vFFAx.ipynb` with x standing for the stage number.

Table 2.2: Design parameters of vFFA lattices.

	Stage 1 vFFA	Stage 4 vFFA
r_0 [m]	953	5570
θ_F [rad]	0.01033	0.00786
N_c	790	1000
β_F [rad]	0.001564	0.001790
β_D [rad]	0.001180	0.001166
γ_F [rad]	0.252	-0.492
m [1/m]	31.94	12.13

Table 2.3: Comparison of vFFA lattices and RCS equivalents [4]. Peak dipole field in the good field region is computed by assuming a normalised transverse emittance of $25 \mu\text{m}$ in both planes, evaluating the projection of the beam size through the cell onto the cartesian xy planes using the Mais-Ripken decoupling parametrisation [6], and applying the scaling law to evaluate the field strength away from the closed orbit.

	RCS1	Stage 1 vFFA	RCS4	Stage 4 vFFA
Circumference [m]	5990	5990	35000	35000
Injection Energy [TeV]	0.06	0.06	1.5	1.5
Extraction Energy [TeV]	0.3	0.3	5	5
NC Ramped Magnets	Yes	No	Yes	No
SC Fixed magnets	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Ramp Rate [T/s]	4200	0	565	0
Vertical Excursion [m]	0	0.048	0	0.12
Relative path length difference	0.0	0.0	1.71×10^{-6}	0.0
Peak Dipole Field On Orbit [T]	1.8 (NC)	6.93	16	13.59
Peak Dipole Field (Good Field Region) [T]		12.52		29.04
Drift length [m]		1.18		1.03
Tune		(0.382, 0.079)		(0.460, 0.057)

3 Decoupled insertions

3.1 Principle

One of the principal difficulties associated with the design of vFFA rings stems from the intrinsically coupled nature of the optics. This presents particular issues in areas such as injection and extraction system design.

To illustrate, we consider the case of a fast extraction in vFFA1. Assuming a kicker strength of 0.2 T, an extraction energy of 300 GeV, and that the kicker occupies the entire drift length of 1 metre, from considering simple geometry, alongside magnetic rigidity, the transverse deflection induced by the kicker at the end of the drift can be evaluated at approximately 0.1 mm. This indicates that extraction within a single drift length is not feasible.

As a consequence, a kicked beam must traverse one or more magnets downstream of the kicker. In conventional machines, this is not in itself an issue; however, for the vFFA, the vertically kicked beam will see a horizontally-

bending dipole field in the next magnet, deflecting it to one side. This means that in the proposed vFFA rings, orbit shifts due to an extraction kicker cannot be confined to a single plane. To accommodate these coupled oscillations of the kicked beam, the magnet gaps would need to be increased horizontally as well as vertically, which would present a significant engineering challenge for high-field magnets.

However, it can be seen from Eq. (2.9) that, in the case that $\gamma = 90^\circ$, the coupling terms in the Hamiltonian vanish. Therefore, if a cell can be engineered such that both magnets have an inclination of 90 degrees, the horizontal and vertical transverse planes of the cell become uncoupled. Equation 2.2 shows that, in the case that $\gamma_F = \gamma_D = 90^\circ$, it is a necessary requirement that $\theta_F = \theta_D$. This means that fully decoupled vFFA lattice cells can be designed - however, only for cells with zero net bending.

Fig. 3.1: 3D geometry of a closed orbit through a half-cell of a vFFA FODO lattice with zero net bending, beginning at the midpoint of the F-magnet and finishing at the midpoint of the D-magnet.

The implication of this for the design of large accelerators based on the vFFA concept is that the inclusion of straight sections enables locally decoupled insertions to be designed. The geometry of closed orbits in straight vFFA FODO cells is also outlined in [3], enabling their design to be approached using the same analytic formalism as for the arc FODO cells. A closed orbit through a vFFA FODO straight cell is illustrated in

Table 3.1: Definitions of all input parameters and output variables that completely specify the geometry of closed orbit through a vFFA FODO lattice with zero bending angle per cell. Definitions are given in terms of Fig. 3.1.

Parameter	Definition	Variable	Definition
L_F	\overline{GJ}	θ_D	$\angle CDE$
L_D	\overline{KH}	ρ_F	$\overline{AF} = \overline{BF}$
L_c	\overline{GM}	ρ_D	$\overline{CD} = \overline{ED}$
θ_F	$\angle AFB$	L_s	\overline{BC}
γ_F	$\angle AFG$	γ_D	$\angle HDE$

Fig. 3.1. The closed orbits of straight vFFA FODO cells are governed by the following set of equations:

$$\theta_D = \theta_F, \quad (3.1)$$

$$\gamma_D = \gamma_F, \quad (3.2)$$

$$\rho_F = \frac{L_F}{\sin \theta_F}, \quad (3.3)$$

$$\rho_D = \frac{L_D}{\sin \theta_D}, \quad (3.4)$$

$$L_s = \frac{L_c - L_F - L_D}{\cos \theta_F}, \quad (3.5)$$

where $L_{F,D}$ are the lengths of the F and D half-magnets depicted in Figure 3.1, and $\theta_{F,D}$ and $\gamma_{F,D}$ the corresponding bending and inclination angles. The radii of curvature associated with the magnets are denoted with the symbols ρ_F and ρ_D . The total length of the cell is specified with L_c , and the length of the drift along the reference orbit is given as L_s . These parameters are defined geometrically using Table 3.1. It can be shown that a straight vFFA cell with an orbit inclination of 90° is entirely equivalent to the straight horizontal-excursion FFA cell proposed and tested in [8].

The inclusion of one or more decoupled straights into the muon accelerator affords the designer a number of additional opportunities. Firstly, the design of extraction or injection systems that require the beam to be kicked over the length of many magnets now becomes feasible. Secondly, the dispersion suppression schemes developed for horizontal-excursion FFA [9, 10] may be applied within these decoupled straights.

3.2 Matching

To minimise unwanted effects from the inclusion of these straight insertions, it will be necessary to ensure a good matching of the optical parameters in the arc sections to those of the straight sections. The first consideration is that the closed orbits must match across all energies. The dispersion in a vFFA is given by

$$D_z = \frac{1}{m}, \quad (3.6)$$

and as a consequence it is a requirement that the m -value be consistent between arc cells and straight cells to ensure proper matching of the closed orbits.

Matching of the linear optical parameters is, however, more subtle. Matching between the u and v decoupled planes associated with the coupled optics in the arc and the Cartesian x and z horizontal and vertical planes of the straight may be non-trivial both due to coupling effects and given the limited number of independent parameters able to be varied in the straight cells.

In the case that a straightforward matching is not achievable, it may be considered to design the straight insertion to have phase advances in both planes that are a multiple of 180° , such that the insertion can be considered transparent with respect to the optics in the rest of the ring. Alternatively, it would be possible to design adiabatic transition sections, in which the inclination angle is slowly varied across the course of a number of arc cells towards 90° from its nominal value in the arcs. However, this would further increase the size of the ring, as these arc cells would necessarily have a larger average radius of curvature in comparison to arc cells with the nominal inclination value.

3.3 Dispersion Suppression

The ability to include dispersion suppressor sections may be critical for the realisation of the muon accelerator vFFA. High-gradient, high-aperture radiofrequency cavities present a large engineering challenge, and the need to reduce betatron oscillations caused by acceleration in dispersive regions limits the amount of acceleration that can be applied in any one area. Having a dispersion-suppressed region would not only reduce the challenges associated with manufacturing the required RF cavities, but may also serve to reduce the requirements for distributed RF, offering a potential to simplify and reduce complexity in terms of the accelerating components. Moreover, if the radiofrequency components can be confined to dispersion-suppressed regions, the restrictions on the design of arc sections will be relaxed, allowing the use of lower m -values. If m -values in the arc can be decreased, this means that - for an equivalent on-orbit dipole field - the pole tip fields may be reduced, either simplifying the magnet requirements or enabling the use of higher on-orbit dipole fields than previously proposed. This also implies additional freedom in the optics design of the arc, relaxing constraints on the choice of working point in the decoupled tunes.

To achieve dispersion suppression, a section comprising three different types of FFA cells must be constructed [9]. The first region has cells with an initial dispersion D_1 , and the final section has cells with the desired final dispersion D_3 . In between are the cells that constitute the actual dispersion suppressor, which have a dispersion D_2 . The dispersion of this region must satisfy

$$D_2 = \frac{D_1 + D_3}{2}, \quad (3.7)$$

which hence determines the m -value of the dispersion suppressor region. A final condition is that the phase advance of the dispersion suppressor in the dispersive plane (in this case the vertical z -plane) must equal 180° . This configuration is illustrated in Figure 3.2, showing how dispersion can be suppressed by making use of the

betatron oscillations about the equilibrium orbit. As the scheme depends on the betatron oscillations being in the dispersive plane, it is a requirement that the dispersion suppressor region D_2 is a decoupled straight with an inclination of 90° .

Fig. 3.2: Schematic representing the FFA dispersion suppressor principle. The red line denoted the reference orbit through the dispersion suppressor region. Note that it is possible for D_3 to be equal to zero for complete dispersion suppression.

It must be noted that this principle relies on linear approximations of the dispersive behaviour, and is valid as long as these approximations hold. A more advanced implementation of this FFA dispersion suppressor scheme has also been studied in the context of horizontal-excursion FFA lattices [10], which - via the modification of field parameters - was able to account for some of the limitations due to the nonlinear fields of the FFA magnets.

4 Conclusions

It has been demonstrated that direct vFFA alternatives to the proposed RCS rings exist with stable optics. These vFFA rings have been shown to have parameters (drift lengths, peak dipole strengths on orbit) within realistic bounds. However, the high m -values required to minimise the excursion (which is a necessity from the perspective of the RF design) limit the accessible parameter space and - crucially - cause fields to rapidly grow away from the closed orbit.

A solution to these issues has been proposed in the form of including RF in decoupled, dispersion-suppressed straights, thereby allowing the arcs to use lower m -values and decreasing the growth of B -fields away from the closed orbit. This may also reduce the needs for distributed RF. Future study will concern the simulation of longitudinal dynamics both in the case of a vFFA with dispersion-suppressed decoupled straights and in the case of a vFFA where RF cavities are distributed throughout the dispersive drifts of regular arc cells.

The lattices proposed using the analytic formalism here must also be verified using numerical simulation, and their non-linear properties studied to ensure the survival of the beam over a large number of turns. Additional iteration of the analytic design may also yield further improvements (such as lower dipole strengths).

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